

Policy Brief no. 3

Seeing Sustainability Differently

New Metrics and Ethical Data Governance for a Just Transition

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Key messages

Innovative data sources are reshaping how we measure sustainability transitions. New data types, ranging from web data to satellite imagery to remote sensing, from behavioral and biometric indicators to outputs from AI systems, may offer powerful tools for understanding transition dynamics.

Novel data can enhance traditional sources if appropriately integrated. While not replacing traditional data sources and conventional methods, other sources can enrich sustainability insights. But this requires common quality standards and methodological rigor, as well as open access to data and scrutability of algorithmic tools and methods.

Without ethical oversight, the use of emerging types of data risks undermining public trust. Novel data raise concerns about quality, validity, privacy, bias, representativity, and legitimacy. Addressing these challenges requires an ethical data governance framework closely linked to methodological integrity.

Indeed, ensuring sound research demands both transparency in algorithmic tools and open access to data. Ethical and methodological considerations are thus deeply intertwined.

Data governance must move beyond compliance to embed values of transparency, participation, inclusion, and accountability. EU institutions and national governments should adopt governance frameworks that ensure AI and data systems are interpretable, auditable, non-biased, and co-designed with stakeholders. They should promote data production by means of citizen science, understood as the active involvement of people in generating, analyzing, and interpreting data for public interest purposes.

A **wide range of data sources** have been identified as **innovative** in supporting the **monitoring of sustainability transitions**.

Public attention is a critical – yet often overlooked – dimension of transition performance.

The analysis of Google Trends reveals evolving public associations with sustainability, underscoring the need to align indicators not just with expert frameworks, but with people's perceptions and concerns.

Citizen science approaches and citizen-generated data have a role to play in sustainability governance.

They enable more inclusive knowledge production, bridging the gap between institutional expertise and local experience. By involving people directly, these approaches can enhance transparency, legitimacy, responsiveness, and the evidence base of environmental decision-making for a just transition.

Ethical data infrastructures and equitable data governance frameworks are not just technical issues – they are strategic enablers of a just and inclusive sustainability transition.

Building legitimacy and effectiveness into just transition monitoring systems is essential to meeting the goals of the European Green Deal, the European Pillar of Social Rights, and the 2030 Agenda.

Background & Context

As Europe confronts the intertwined challenges of climate change and environmental degradation, social inequality, economic uncertainty, demographic change, and democratic backsliding, as well as pressing geopolitical challenges, the ability to monitor and guide sustainability transitions is more critical than ever. Addressing this complexity requires new ways of measuring progress – approaches that reflect the dynamic, contested, and interdependent nature of contemporary societal transitions.

Despite decades of policy attention, measuring sustainability transitions remains a contested and evolving task. Existing indicators – primarily grounded in economic metrics or static environmental benchmarks – struggle to capture the complexity, interconnectedness, and lived experience of sustainability transitions. They privilege what is easily measurable over what is meaningful, overlooking key dimensions such as social justice, public perceptions, and community resilience. Meanwhile, the data infrastructures underpinning these indicators are frequently fragmented, outdated, or inaccessible.

Conventional data sources – such as national statistics or structured surveys – remain essential but are increasingly inadequate on their own. They are often too slow, too coarse-grained, or too narrowly scoped to reflect the fast-changing dynamics of environmental degradation, social inequality, and technological disruption that define today's transition contexts. As a result, the demand for more dynamic and integrated approaches to data and measurement is growing.

The SPES project (Sustainability Performances, Evidence and Scenarios) responds to this challenge by rethinking how evidence is produced and used to support a just and sustainable future. At the heart of SPES is the recognition that traditional data sources alone are insufficient to capture the complexity of contemporary sustainability challenges. Instead, SPES identifies a wide range of novel and complex data sources – from web analytics to citizen-generated data (CGD) – that offer new opportunities for monitoring transitions across scales and contexts.

Novel and complex data sources – from web analytics to citizen-generated data – offer new opportunities for **monitoring transitions across scales and contexts.**

Often generated outside institutional settings or in real time, these alternative data streams can capture behavioral patterns, public perceptions, and emergent dynamics that conventional sources miss. SPES highlights the innovative potential of repurposing data originally collected for other purposes – such as engineering, marketing, or administrative tasks – and creatively combining traditional and non-traditional sources to generate actionable insights. Yet, it also emphasizes the need for robust methods of data integration and harmonization to ensure consistency and policy relevance, including the creation of synthetic datasets and use of visual tools for transparency.

From satellite imagery and sensor data to web analytics and people-generated information, new types of data can help capture patterns of behavior, perception, and impact that remain invisible to traditional tools – provided they are methodologically integrated, ethically governed, and generated and deployed with attention to inclusivity and legitimacy. Furthermore, emerging frontiers of data generation invite us to consider not only alternative but also yet-to-come sources of data.

These include, for example: (1) data from human interactions with Large Language Models (LLMs) and other Artificial Intelligence systems; (2) anthropometric – such as measurements of body size, shape, or movement – and behavioral data inferred through surveillance; and (3) socio-economic data generated through tokens (such as those used in blockchain systems or loyalty programs), digital platforms, and complementary currencies. But while these novel data forms hold promise for monitoring the sustainability transition in new ways, they also raise concerns about quality, validity, privacy, bias, inclusion, and legitimacy.

By challenging dominant data regimes and questioning whose knowledge counts, SPES advances an approach to monitoring that reimagines how ecological and social transitions are managed, who produces knowledge, and how data can empower rather than exclude. This vision is foundational to building more legitimate, accountable, and inclusive systems – capable of supporting the goals of the European Green Deal, the European Pillar of Social Rights, and the 2030 Agenda – but only if new forms of evidence and engagement are embraced.

SPES Evidence

Meeting today's sustainability challenges requires **going beyond traditional data and conventional methods**, toward more dynamic and integrated approaches.

The SPES project explores how novel data sources and methods can enrich our understanding of sustainability transitions. By experimenting with unconventional forms of evidence and data integration, SPES demonstrates the value and challenges of using alternative data to inform policymaking and public engagement.

A wide range of data sources have been identified as innovative in supporting the monitoring of sustainability transitions, as defined by the SPES framework. These include CGD, satellite imagery, administrative and governmental data, big urban data, web data, and financial transaction data, as well as data generated through remote sensing, crowdsourced platforms, and social media. These alternative data streams, usually produced in real time or outside institutional settings, are increasingly central to tracking transition performances across diverse contexts and scales.

Innovation often stems from creatively adapting data generated for unrelated fields or institutional functions as well as from creatively combining traditional and non-traditional sources. Yet, such practices raise challenges.

Public concerns about sustainability are growing across Europe, and **people have a vital role to play in generating data that can help understand and guide the sustainability transition.**

Data not designed for sustainability research may lack representativity or reliability. Integrating datasets – from official statistics to social media – requires harmonization methods that ensure methodological consistency and policy relevance. SPES has identified practical strategies to address these issues, including synthetic datasets, blended surveys, visual decision tools, and software-enabled workflows.

One example is the analysis of Google Trends data, which provided insights into how people across EU member states engage with sustainability discourses. The results revealed a steady increase in public interest over time, along with significant regional variations. These findings highlight the value of perception-based and behavioral data as complements to traditional institutional metrics.

This novel approach emphasizes the importance of ensuring access to platform data for public interest research – for example, to understand and anticipate patterns of civic engagement across member states. While this form of analysis incorporates public opinion dynamics, it still depends on top-down categories and corporate-driven data collection.

Citizen-generated data, by contrast, offer a grassroots alternative. Rooted in experiential knowledge, CGD includes forms such as citizen sensing and participatory environmental monitoring. These practices support transparency, inform policy, and foster community engagement. A relevant example is the use of low-cost sensors to monitor air quality and tropospheric ozone.

Depending on its purpose and use, CGD can support policy development, enhance transparency and evidence-based decision-making, and strengthen public engagement. Yet its broader uptake is constrained by persistent barriers: unclear data ownership, fragile technical infrastructure, challenges in sustaining engagement, exclusion from governance frameworks, and limited recognition in science and policy.

Taken together, these insights affirm the need for more pluralistic and inclusive evidence systems – ones that reflect the lived realities of communities and the complexity of transitions. SPES contributes to this shift by demonstrating how alternative data practices can expand what counts as evidence in sustainability governance.

The following policy recommendations are designed to address the key challenges identified here.

Policy recommendations

01.

Establish **EU-wide guidelines for ethical use and harmonization of novel data** in transition monitoring.

To strengthen the legitimacy and effectiveness of sustainability monitoring, the EU should establish ethical guidelines and minimum technical standards for the use of emerging data sources. These must address privacy, fairness, representativity, and accountability – especially for industry-led data (e.g., social media, platforms) and novel types (e.g., sensors, IoT, citizen science) – while remaining flexible for future data (e.g., LLM interactions, complementary currency data).

In parallel, ensuring the comparability and policy relevance of transition indicators requires cross-border harmonization. The EU should foster coordination among member states to align methodologies and integrate diverse data sources by expanding Eurostat's infrastructure to include new data types. This dual focus on ethical governance and interoperability will support robust, comparative analyses across countries, regions, sectors, and population groups.

02.

Promote **open, transparent transition data**, fund **public datasets**, and require **method scrutability** in all EU-funded programs.

Public-facing datasets are vital for fostering transparency, accountability, and people's engagement in sustainability transitions – yet they remain under-resourced. Starter funds can help launch and sustain open datasets that track key sustainability indicators, enable cross-regional and cross-group comparisons, and support evidence-based policymaking. This, in turn, strengthens democratic access to information and fosters innovation in how sustainability performance is measured and communicated.

In addition to mandating open data, EU-funded projects, particularly those addressing sustainability, should adopt open methodology principles – such as the use of open-source software and algorithmic transparency – to allow third parties to scrutinize how sustainability data is produced and to build upon these results.

03.

Require **GDPR-compliant access to platform data**, with safeguards for vulnerable communities.

Platforms and digital services operating within the EU (e.g., web browsers, social media, sensors) should meet minimum standards for third-party access to data generated within EU borders, to support evidence-based policymaking and public interest research. This access – available to public authorities, researchers, and civil society – must be compliant with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other relevant legislation, standardized, non-discriminatory, and include clear procedures for responsible use.

At the same time, policy frameworks must protect communities and territories, especially disadvantaged ones, from the unintended consequences of data openness. Freely accessible data can affect real estate, competition, or expose regions to pressure. Making people, activities, or places “legible” through data must not come at the cost of resilience.

04.

Recognize **citizen-generated data** and embed **public participation in environmental governance**.

Citizen-generated data, grounded in lived experience and community knowledge, enhances democratic legitimacy and local relevance in sustainability transition monitoring. EU institutions should support people’s participation in both data collection and validation, integrating CGD with institutional sources through inclusive processes such as citizen panels and co-design workshops.

To fully leverage CGD, the EU should establish a robust regulatory framework and quality standards that recognize it as a valid and legitimate source alongside expert data. This would ensure its inclusion in policy consultations and assessments, bridging the gap between institutional practices and people-led contributions, and fostering more accountable, trusted governance.

Policy recommendations

05.

Strengthen **public sector data literacy** and capacity building and **embed people's participation in data governance**.

Improving data literacy is key for navigating the complexity of sustainability data. EU funding should support comprehensive training and capacity-building for policymakers, public administrations, and people programs – especially from underrepresented groups – at both EU and local levels. Expanding the European Skills agenda initiatives, programs should cover interpreting emerging data sources and understanding the ethical dimensions of AI-supported tools. This is pivotal to increasing capabilities and to fostering individual and collective human agency (i.e. the commitment over one's well-being and the well-being of 'others', including nature at large). For these reasons, in parallel, public participation should be embedded in institutional processes through panels, co-design workshops, and deliberative forums.

These participatory processes help ensure data governance is transparent, inclusive, and accountable—enhancing both democratic legitimacy and public trust in data-driven policymaking.

Alternative data practices can expand what counts as evidence in **sustainability governance**.

Glossary

AI systems / algorithmic tools.

Computational systems capable of processing data, recognizing patterns, and making decisions or predictions.

Big urban data. Large-scale datasets generated in urban environments, often from sensors, mobile devices, social media, and infrastructure systems, used to analyze and manage city life.

Blended surveys. Research methods that combine traditional surveys with alternative data sources to improve coverage, responsiveness, or representativeness.

Citizen science. Scientific research conducted, in whole or in part, by non-professional scientists (citizens), often involving data collection, analysis, and knowledge sharing.

Citizen sensing. A form of citizen science where individuals or communities use sensors (e.g., for air quality) to monitor environmental conditions and generate local data.

Co-design / participatory processes.

Approaches that involve stakeholders, especially laypersons, in shaping research, policies, and technologies that affect them.

Complementary currencies / tokens.

Alternative economic instruments, such as blockchain tokens or local currencies, that can generate socio-economic data relevant to transitions.

Data-driven policymaking / governance.

The practice of using empirical data to guide the design, implementation, and evaluation of public policies.

Data harmonization. The process of aligning and integrating diverse datasets to make them comparable and analytically compatible across different contexts.

Data legibility. The visibility and comprehensibility of data about people or places, which can enable governance but also pose risks like surveillance or exploitation.

Data literacy. The ability to understand, interpret, and use data effectively, a critical skill for policymakers, civil society, and the public in data-driven governance.

Data openness / open access. The principle that data, especially data generated with public resources, should be freely available for use, reuse, and scrutiny.

GDPR compliance. Adherence to the General Data Protection Regulation, which governs personal data protection and privacy in the European Union.

Interoperability. The ability of different data systems and software to communicate, exchange, and use information effectively, enabling cross-border or cross-sector analysis.

Novel data / alternative data. Non-traditional data sources such as web activity, sensor outputs, satellite imagery, platform data, biometric data, or AI-generated content, that can be used to complement official statistics.

Methodological integrity. The application of sound, rigorous, and transparent research methods that ensure the validity and reproducibility of data analysis and results.

Platform data. Data generated through interactions with digital platforms (e.g., social media, e-commerce, browsers), often held by private companies but valuable for public interest research.

Public attention / perception data. Data reflecting public interest, attitudes, or concerns (e.g., Google Trends), used to align policy with citizen values and awareness.

Public participation. The active involvement of individuals and communities in decision-making processes, including data collection, interpretation, and governance. Public participation helps ensure that sustainability transitions are inclusive, transparent, and responsive to local needs and knowledge.

Remote sensing. The use of satellite or aerial sensor technologies to detect and monitor physical characteristics of an area, often used in environmental and climate monitoring.

Synthetic data. Artificially generated data that mimics real datasets, used for analysis or model training while protecting privacy or compensating for missing data.

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